

TEACHING FUTURE PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS TO ORGANIZE A LESSON BASED ON CREATIVITY

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Abstract. *Through this article, an opinion is made on the issues of developing creativity in future elementary school teachers, on the basis of this, forming aspects of a creative approach to the organization of lessons.*

Keywords: *future primary school teacher, primary school students, primary education, creativity.*

Due to the strengthening of innovative processes, involving students in educational and scientific projects, organizing creative activity classes with them, creating free and creative decision-making in various types of activities in students, encouraging them to freely express their thoughts, also, the question of teaching to invent, understand and master new things is becoming more relevant. And this, in turn, imposes a certain serious task on the specialist who organizes the lesson. It means that the teacher should have creativity. At the same time, it should be emphasized that it helps the teacher and students to acquire self-awareness and additional creative development skills.

Taking into account the age characteristics and physical aspects of primary school students, it is necessary to pay attention to a creative approach to the lessons. It is important to convey the importance of this issue to future teachers in the process of training future primary school teachers. It is necessary to inform students that special attention is paid to this in regulatory documents.

It is one-sided that a person can be creative. If the surrounding creation is perceived with a certain depth, then what is perceived can be imitated, combined and changed in various ways and appear very creative to others. But in fact, this is not true creativity. Everything that can be created already exists in the universe.

As Sadhguru said, man is a master craftsman capable of the most. If creativity is defined as creating something, whether it's a film, a painting, a building, a speech, or whatever, it's not real creativity - it's a skillful imitation. Due to the fact that attention is paid to various aspects of life, it is also human who is able to create imitations of others in an incredible way. If the word "imitation" seems out of place in this process, the word "imitation" can be used.

So, based on the above thoughts, it can be concluded that in teaching future primary school teachers to organize lessons based on creativity, it is necessary to teach them to create a new idea from a lesson process, method, not copying. it is. Then it will be possible to increase the demand of the future primary education teacher to always work at his own best in the process of teaching in primary classes. This serves as a basis for the continuous introduction of innovations in the lessons and the awakening of repeated interest of elementary school students.

Primary school teachers play a special role in forming elementary school students as knowledgeable and intellectually mature people, in forming their internal psychological

orientation to science, education, and acquiring knowledge. It is the primary school teacher who acts as a role model for students. Especially in elementary grades, the first teacher (muallima) is embodied as a great breed for elementary school students and appears as a role model in the eyes of students. Therefore, the creativity of primary school teachers is very important, along with their ability to understand students, communicative and perceptive skills. After all, it has been scientifically proven by psychologists that elementary school students have a strong motivation, curiosity, and desire to learn. It is only necessary to direct such interests and passions in a positive direction. This requires more research, creativity and innovation from primary school teachers. In the formation of these characteristics, the importance of the training process of future primary school teachers and paying attention to the competency approach is considered high.

It is known that the issue of creative activity of teachers has been scientifically studied by pedagogic scientists and researchers, among them, creativity of primary school teachers is considered as one of the main issues. Among them, creativity is an important pedagogical problem. Researches, studies and many studies in this regard have reached the level of today's demand.

In the conditions of modern globalization and informatization of education, the creative activity of the teacher is of great importance. Innovative innovations entering the field of education today bring new concepts to the science of pedagogy. It is no secret that one of such concepts is the concept of "creativity". This concept was more widely developed in psychology. But today, the science of pedagogy also requires research into the content and meaning of this concept.

The concept of "creativity" is related to the concept of "creativity". The social order to research the creative possibilities of the individual determines that the problem of creativity is special and important.

It should also be said that creativity is an integral part of human spirituality as a personality-developing category, a factor of self-development of a person, the basis of personal vitality, not in the multifaceted nature of the knowledge possessed by a person, but in new ideas. It is manifested in striving and in reforming and changing the process of creating new stereotypes, making unexpected and unusual decisions in the process of solving life problems. In this case, the creative activity of the primary education teacher is primarily related to his pedagogical skills.

Every primary school teacher should be able to show his/her creativity during the lesson, create a positive impression on primary school students, have a creative approach to the lesson and conduct the lesson in a quality and meaningful way using various modern methods. This is one of the most urgent issues of the day. Therefore, it is very important to teach every future elementary school teacher that they need to constantly work on themselves and understand what creativity is and apply it positively to the teaching process. It is necessary to teach future primary school teachers that every teacher conduct lessons with a creative approach to the lesson, and that each lesson ends in a meaningful and comprehensible state for the student.

Raising a healthy and well-rounded generation in primary education is realizing the creative and intellectual potential of young people, by widely introducing modern information and communication and pedagogical technologies, electronic textbooks, and multimedia tools into the educational process. One of our urgent tasks is to fundamentally improve and further develop the quality of teaching. That is why it is important to achieve the main goal of primary education, that is, to form a positive attitude to reading in the student, to develop reading literacy, to teach students to work with various information, to learn the basic language. quality education in elementary grades to achieve thorough knowledge of their information and be able to apply it in everyday life,

to form logical and creative thinking in them, to teach them to acquire the norms of written and oral communication, and to be able to self-control and self-control. Special attention should be paid to the organization of agricultural activities. For this, first of all, the professional potential and level of education of the primary school teacher, knowledge of child psychology, modern primary education methods are important in improving the quality of primary education. Developing creativity in future elementary school teachers is also an urgent problem in promoting the importance of this in practice.

Taking into account that future primary school teachers are brought up in the conditions of innovative education, it is important to form in them the ability to organize classes with new ideas based on innovative technologies. This will increase the level of innovative knowledge not only of the future elementary school teacher, but also of the students he will teach in the future. The most important thing is that elementary school classes are organized in a way that is interesting and full of necessary information. Also, the opportunity to increase students' activity in the learning process will increase.

In order to develop the creativity of future elementary school teachers, it is also beneficial to inform them about the changes in modern educational processes. Because these innovations will help students to create and save ideas for future lesson processes. It should be said that when teaching future elementary school teachers to organize a lesson based on creativity, they should develop the ability to work with a plan and organize the lesson step by step based on this plan. This will ensure consistency of the methods and tools they use in the lesson process, and as a result, they will have a predictive idea about the final part of the lesson.

As a conclusion to the above points, it is considered permissible to emphasize the following: The fact that the children of the present era are the future of the motherland encourages primary school teachers to work responsibly. And on this basis, today's elementary school teacher should organize the lesson in such a way that the student feels good. And the sequence of appropriate methods in games and tasks, lesson topics should be directed towards efficiency. Don't forget that creative ideas, games, assignments, and methods taught by various teachers are based on a well-rounded human education.

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